

In general the metal chelates display 1:2 metal-ligand stoichiometry. The molecular weight data suggest the composition $[ML_2]$ for these compounds, where M = metal-ion and LH = HFB or HFP. Their magnetic moments indicate the presence of 4, 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 unpaired electron, respectively in the Cr(II), Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates.

A perusal of the μ_{eff} value suggest these complexes to be high-spin ones.

The data shown in Table 1 suggest nearly octahedral structure for these chelates. However, Cu(II) chelates may possess square-planar or tetragonally distorted octahedral structure in terms of Jahn-Teller effect⁶.

I. R. spectra of HFB and HFP show bands in the ranges of 2570-2560 cm^{-1} , 1690-1680 cm^{-1} and 1610-1600 cm^{-1} assignable to γ COOH, γ C-O and γ C-N, respectively. In the spectra of the metal chelates the bands in the range 2570-2560 cm^{-1} disappeared suggesting co-ordination through the carboxylate group and appearance of bands in the region 1560-1620 cm^{-1} and 1300-1380 cm^{-1} indicate γ_{as} (COO⁻) and γ_s (COO⁻), respectively. γ C-N of the ligands in the range 1610-1600 cm^{-1} was shifted to lower frequency side. On chelation suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in co-ordination. The appearance of two new bands in the ranges of 620-610 cm^{-1} and 550-540 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates indicate the formation of M-O and M-N bonds respectively in them. As regards the heterogeneity of γ M-O band, it appears that perhaps due to interference by ligand molecule it is not discernible⁷.

The very low conductance values of the chelates in dioxan and DMF at room temperature suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The results so far obtained conclusively show that the general similarities of the chelates of HFB and HFP are not due to the presence or absence of an open chain or a six membered ring but it is due to the presence of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group in β -position to the carboxylic group.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to University Grants Commission (UGC) for the award of fellowship to one of them (N.K.S.).

References

1. R.H. HOLM, G.W. EVERETTE (JR) and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
2. PERRY, L. CHRISTOPHER, Webber and James Harold, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 1031.
3. R. K. MEHTA and R. K. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 56.
4. B. N. FIGGIS and C. M. HARRIS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855.
5. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 6, 37.
6. H. A. JAHN and E. TELLER, *Prog. R. Soc.*, 1937, 161, 220.
7. J. R. WAGNER and D. G. HENDRICKER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 1375.

Isolation and Characterization of Methyl N,N¹ ethylenebis (salicylidene iminato) cobalt (III)- μ -cyano-methyl-bis (dimethyl glyoximato) cobalt (III) anion as Tetra-Phenyl arsonium and Tetra ethyl ammonium Salts

K. DEY*, R. L. DE and J. K. BHAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani-741 235, Nadia, West Bengal

Manuscript received 18 June 1976, revised 1 June 1979,
accepted 6 October 1979.

CYANO-COMPLEXES of cobalt, in its various oxidation states, are well known¹. Bridged cyanide complexes have also been postulated as intermediates^{2,3} in some inner-sphere electron transfer reaction of cyano cobalt compounds, and several such bridged complexes have been isolated⁴⁻⁷. Very few organo cyano cobalt (III) complexes are known in the solid state, although some of them are known to be formed in solution⁸.

One of our recent interests is to study the synthetic methods, reactivities and structural elucidation of some organo-derivatives of transition metal Schiff base complexes and analogous complexes⁹. It has been recognized for some time that the ligands trans to a σ -bonded alkyl substituent undergo substitution of rate much higher than the same ligand in similar compounds lacking the M-C σ bond¹⁰⁻¹⁷. This note describes our observations on the reactions of methyl aquo-N,N¹ ethylenebis (salicylidene iminato) cobalt (III), CH_3Co (Salen) H_2O (I)⁹, with tetra phenyl arsonium/or tetra ethylammonium salt (S) of methyl bis(dimethyl glyoximato) cyano cobaltate (III), $M^+ [CH_3Co(dmg)CN]$ (when, $M^+ = Ph_4As^+$ (II)⁸ or Et_4N^+ (III)⁸) and the isolation and characterisation of the title cyano bridged complex, $M^+ [CH_3Co(salen)CNCo(dmg)H]_2[CH_3]^-$ (when $M^+ = Ph_4As$ (IV) and $M^+ = Et_4N$ (V)).

Treatment of (I) with the chloroform solution of (II) at $\sim 60^\circ$ yielded a brown solution. This brown solution, on treating with dry ether, gave a brown crystalline cyano-bridged complexes (IV). Analogously, the cyano bridged complex (V) was obtained when (I) was treated with (III). The molecular weight of (IV) supports its formulation. Besides, very satisfactory elemental analysis of C, H and N were obtained for (IV) and (V). (Found for (IV) : C, 58.38 ; H, 5.72 ; N, 9.58 ; Co, 11.09 / ; M. wt. 1028. Calcd. for (IV) : C, 58.13 ; H, 5.13 ; N, 9.31 ; Co, 11.19 / M. wt. 1052.7. Found for (V) : C, 52.00 ; H, 6.97 ; N, 14.13 ; Co, 14.79 / ; Calcd. for (V) : C, 52.52 ; H, 6.75 ; N, 14.01 ; Co, 4.7 /).

The bridging nature of cyanide ions in these two complexes (IV) and (V) has been demonstrated by the cyanide stretching frequencies observed (at 2150 cm^{-1} and 2148 cm^{-1} respectively) in these two complexes⁸. The formation of bridged complexes has an effect on the infrared absorption of the bridged ligand. The cyanide stretching vibrations increase by a fairly constant increment over that of the monomeric complexes,

i.e., $+ 32 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, in agreement with the change predicted for bridge formation¹⁹. However, from the present results we are not sure whether nitrogen end of CN^- is coordinated to cobalt atom of $\text{Co}(\text{salen})\text{CH}_3$ moiety or to $\text{Co}(\text{dmgH})_2\text{CH}_3$ moiety. In this respect it may be mentioned that linkage isomerisms of a bridging cyanide group is possible in $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co NC Co}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co CN Co}(\text{CN})_5\text{H}_2\text{O}^{19}$. Labilizations of trans ligand (here water molecule) by σ -bonded methyl group might help to form the cyano-bridged complexes (IV) and (V).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for a Senior Research Fellowship to one of them (R.L.D.) and also to U.G.C., New Delhi for some financial assistance. Thanks are also due to Dr. P. K. Sengupta, Department of Organic Chemistry, University of Zurich for micro analysis.

References

1. B. M. CHADWICK and A. G. SHARP, *Adv. Inorg. Chem., Radio Chem.*, 1966, 8, 83,
2. J. HALPERN and S. NAKAMURA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 87, 3002.
3. J. P. BIRK and J. H. ESPENSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 1153.
4. A. HAIM and W. K. WILMARTH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 509.
5. R. A. deCASTELLO, C. P. MAC-COLL, N. B. EGEN and A. HAIM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, 8, 699.
6. R. A. deCASTELLO, C. P. MAC-COLL and A. HAIM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 203.
7. N. B. EGEN and R. A. KRAUSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 11, 1327.
8. D. DODD and M. D. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 1218; 1974, 58.
9. K. DEY and R. L. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 374; K. DEY, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1974, 33, 76; K. DEY, unpublished results.
10. J. M. PRATT and R. G. THORP, *Adv. Inorg. Radio Chem.*, 1969, 12, 375.
11. G. C. HAYWARD, H. A. O. HILL, J. M. PRATT and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 196.
12. D. THUSIUS, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 1183; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 93, 3629.
13. A. L. CRUMBLISH and W. K. WILMARTH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 92, 2593.
14. T. SAKURAI, J. P. FOX and L. L. INGRAHAM, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, 10, 1105.
15. K. L. BROWN and R. G. KALLESS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 1894; K. L. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 6697.
16. H. A. O. HILL, K. G. MORALLEE, G. PELLIZER, G. MESTRONI and G. COSTA, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1968, 11, 167.
17. G. COSTA, G. MESTRONI, G. TOUZHER, D. M. GOODALL, M. GREEN and H. A. O. HILL, *Chem. Comm.*, 1970, 34; G. TOUZHER, *et. al. J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.*, 1973, 413.
18. D. A. DOWS, A. HAIM and W. K. WILMARTH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 21, 33.
19. I. R. FRONCZEK and W. P. SCHAEFER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 13, 727.

Redox Reactions in Non-aqueous Media. Determination of Alkyl/Arylammonium Alkyl/Aryldithiocarbamates with Iodine and Iodine Halides

BALBIR CHAND VERMA and SWATANTAR KUMAR

Chemistry Department, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005 (India)

Manuscript received 22 July 1977, revised 5 June 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

NON-AQUEOUS solvents are important for the redox determination of those compounds which are slightly soluble in water or react with it through hydrolysis or oxidation, or are decomposed by the media of aqueous redox titrations. The problems associated with the redox determination in aqueous media of dithiocarbamates, firstly because of their tendency to undergo decomposition with acids which serve as the media of aqueous redox titrations and secondly because of the interference of their insoluble oxidation products (thiuram disulphides), can be avoided if non-aqueous redox methods are used for the purpose. However, most of such work has been reported for water soluble dithiocarbamates. Verma and Kumar^{1,2} have recently described the use of iodine, iodine halides and N-bromosuccinimide (in acetonitrile) for the determination of these compounds in acetonitrile medium. Paul *et al.*^{3,4} carried out the determination of these compounds potentiometrically with iodine cyanide in alcohol, alcohol-chloroform or acetone medium; and with bromide cyanide in alcohol or acetonitrile medium.

Monoalkyl/arylammonium monoalkyl/aryldithiocarbamates and dialkyl/arylammonium dialkyl/aryldithiocarbamates which are prepared^{5,6} through the reactions of primary and secondary amines with carbon disulphide in organic solvents, have been put to various uses⁵. These compounds, unlike sodium/potassium salts of dithiocarbamic acid, are only sparingly soluble in water and hence the determination of these compounds by non-aqueous redox methods has the added advantage. No effort in this direction appears to have been made.

The present communication reports the direct visual and potentiometric non-aqueous redox determination of these compounds with iodine and iodine halides using acetonitrile as a solvent both for the preparation of oxidant solution as well as media of titration. The potentiometric titrations have been performed using a bright platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified -calomel or antimony electrode as reference electrode. The proposed method for the determination of alkyl/arylammonium alkyl/aryldithiocarbamates are simple, rapid, accurate and widely applicable.

Experimental

Reagents and Equipment; Acetonitrile of BDH quality was distilled twice over phosphorus pentoxide (5 g/l).